
ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF *OCIMUM GRATISSIMUM* LEAF EXTRACT ON SOME SELECTED UROPATHOGENS ISOLATED FROM UTI PATIENTS ATTENDING FEDERAL UNIVERSITY TEACHING HOSPITAL LAFIA, NIGERIA

Peter Uteh Upla¹, Safiya Sani Osagede², Uyi Osuyi Gerard¹

¹Department of Microbiology, Federal University of Lafia, Nigeria

²Isa Mustapha Agwai I Polytechnic Lafia, Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Email: peter.upla@science.fulafia.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

Urinary tract infection (UTIs) is a serious public health problem as a result of multidrug resistance of mostly infecting Gram-negative bacteria. This study aimed to determine the efficacy of *Ocimum gratissimum* against bacteria isolated from UTI patients at the Federal University Teaching Hospital, Lafia. Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) was used to characterize the organic compounds present in *Ocimum gratissimum*. The isolates were identified using polymerase chain reaction (PCR). The agar well diffusion and microdilution broth techniques were used to determine antibacterial susceptibility test and minimum inhibitory concentration. The bacteria isolated includes *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus mirabilis* and *Klebsiella*. Characterization of the organic compounds present in ethanol and methanol extract of *O. gratissimum* revealed that the most abundant compounds in ethanol extract of *O. gratissimum* were 3-methyl-4-isopropylphenol (59.5%), and the least abundant were 5-hydroxy-2,2,6,6-tetramethyl-4-cyclohexane-1,3-dione (2.140%). While the most abundant compounds in methanol extract were 3-methyl-4-isopropylphenol (52.281%), and the least were Heptanoic acid, 3-methylbutyl ester, 4-methyl-cyclohex-2-en-1-ol (1.789%). The PCR result revealed that *Klebsiella*, *Proteus*, and *Escherichia coli* express the gene blaTEM and blaSHV, *Proteus mirabilis* express the gene blaCTEX-M-4. Result of the diameter zone of inhibition, ethanol extraction of *O. gratissimum* showed inhibition zone of 13.5mm and 11.8mm against *Escherichia coli* at 250mg/mL, while the aqueous extract produced an 11mm zone of inhibition. *Proteus*

mirabilis and *Klebsiella* were resistant to the extract at the least concentration of 31.3mg/mL. The minimum inhibitory concentration revealed that the extract of *O. gratissimum* inhibited the urine pathogens at a higher concentration and the MIC values ranged between 62.5-31.3mg/mL. The result revealed that water and methanol extract of *O. gratissimum* were better extraction solvents and this plant present a potential alternative for treatment of UTIs

Keywords; *Ocimum gratissimum*, PCR, treatment, Urinary tract infection, Minimum

INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, urine was historically considered to be a sterile liquid, and many scientists have carried out experiments in order to investigate and confirm urinary tract infections (UTIs). In many cases, urine is not sterile; it contains urinary microbiota (Al-Hilu and Al-Shujairi, 2024). Urinary tract infections are considered the most common infections that massively affect women. The occurrence of urinary tract infection depends on anatomical factors, the integrity of host defense mechanisms, as well as the virulence of the infecting organisms (Nicolle, 2002). It is estimated that over 40-50% of women will experience urinary tract infection in their life time while the rate is only 5% in men (Ulett *et al.*, 2013). Some of the risk factors that make women more sensitive to urinary tract infections than men are the female anatomy; oestrogen deficiency, shorter urethra, and birth control (Abass *et al.*, 2014; Yatouli, 2010). Urinary tract infections are classified into disease categories based on the site of infection; pyelonephritis (the kidney), cystitis (the bladder), and bacteriuria (the urine) (Foxman, 2003). Approximately 80% of Urinary tract infections

are caused by strains of Uropathogenic *Escherichia coli*, a Gram-negative, rod shaped, flagellated, facultative anaerobic, opportunistic, and intracellular pathogenic microorganism (Sadler, 1989). Uropathogenic *Escherichia coli* (UPEC) strains are the primary cause of urinary tract infection (UTI), affecting mostly women (Stamm, 2001).

They have wide range of virulence factors and strategies required for adhesion to the cells, colonization, invasion and persistence within the host urinary tract. This strain also causes Pyelonephilitis, Cystitis and complicated infection that may result in acute renal failure in healthy host and renal transplant patients (Justyna *et al.*, 2012).

Urinary tract infection (UTI) which was caused mostly by Gram negative bacteria, predominately by *Escherichia coli* and by mixed infections of Gram-positive bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, including other Gram-negative bacteria, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Enterobacter aerogenes*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Citrobacter freundii*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Klebsiella oxytoca*, which used to play minimal roles, have now assumed significant places as etiological agents of UTI (Mishra *et al.*, 2013). If any infection in a patient is not controlled, infecting microbes develop resistance to the administered antibiotics intrinsically and a drug-resistant cell will survive and predominates with concomitant bacterial genetic exchanges mechanisms (McMurry and Levy, 2011). In short, there are several factors of antibiotic resistance in pathogenic bacteria and this situation has become a clinical consternation. A physician often prescribes some higher generation antibiotics in empiric therapy to avoid the debacle from treatment failure arising from the possible presence of MDR bacteria. And the UTI being a graver problem than imagined because of frequent attacks in females mainly, some complementary/adjuvant/synergistic therapeutic strategy is warranted.

Ocimum gratissimum popularly referred to as scent leaf because of its aroma is commonly used as spices for food or soup preparation in Nigeria. It is a medicinal plant which has been used traditionally for the treatment of various infections (Abdullahi, 2012). The plant is cultivated in abundant in different part of Nigeria and it contains some bioactive substances such as tannin, saponins, alkaloids, glycosides, phenols and flavonoids. These phytochemicals when consumed serve as medicine for the protection and treatment of human or animal disease (Abdullahi, 2012). The in-vitro antimicrobial screening of *O.*

gratissimum against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *E. coli*, *Streptococcus fecalis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Lactobacilli* showed that the leaf extract is effective against human pathogens. Mineral elements are necessary for human life and can either be advantageous or detrimental. At least 60 chemical components are detected in the human body. But according to Nielsen (1999), approximately 25 of these are thought to be involved in the body's normal functioning. This study aimed to determine the antibacterial activity of *Ocimum gratissimum* against urine isolates from patient attending Federal University Teaching Hospital, Lafia, Nasarawa State.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study area

The study was conducted in Lafia, the capital of Nasarawa state and lies between latitude 8°25'40" N to 8°34'15" N and longitude 8°24'25" E to 8°38'19" E in the guinea savannah region of northern Nigeria. It has a population of 1,863,275 (2006 census figures) with a population density of 65 people/square kilometres. Its population makes up 1.3% of Nigeria's total population. Nasarawa State is characterized by a tropical sub-humid climate with two distinct seasons.

Study Population

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Suspected UTI Patients of all Age groups of both sexes from 0 years and above presented to the in-patients and out-patients of Microbiology Laboratory of Federal University Teaching Hospital Lafia. However, pregnant women were excluded from the study.

Ethical Approval and Consent

For the success of this study, ethical approvals were obtained from the Management Board of Federal University Teaching Hospital Lafia. Photocopies and originals of these approval letters were presented at the Federal University Teaching Hospital Lafia, Nasarawa State where subsequent endorsement letters were issued to the Head of Laboratory Unit, and were delivered to the patients. The patients were

informed of the need to be part of the study by trying to provide urine samples for laboratory diagnoses.

Sample Size

The sample size for the research was 210 Samples. This is calculated from the study done by Imam *et al.* (2019).

$$N = \frac{Z^2 P(1-P)}{d^2}$$

Where N= Minimum sample size.

Z= Normal standard deviation for a normal distribution taken 95% confidence interval which corresponds to 1.96P Expected from literature available (16.09%) and D=Degree of activity set at 0.05 for 95% confidence interval

$$N = 1.96^2 \times 0.1609 (1-0.1609) / 0.0025$$

$$N = 0.61811 \times 0.8291 / 0.0025$$

$$N = 0.5186 / 0.0025. N = 207.46, N = 210$$

Collection of Plant Materials

Fresh leaves of *Ocimum gratissimum* (Scent leaf) was obtained from home garden in Doma Local Government of Nasarawa State, Nigeria and then transported to the Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology for authentication.

Collection of Urine samples

A mid-stream urine samples was collected from suspected UTI patients of all age groups who were presented to the Outpatient and Inpatient Departments of Microbiology laboratory of Federal University Teaching Hospital, Lafia, Nasarawa State, Nigeria with complaints of dysuria, increased frequency and urgency of voiding, suprapubic discomfort or joint pain and fever.

Preparation of Extracts

Preparation of Water Extracts of Ocimum grattisimum

The freshly collected leaves of *Ocimum gratissimum* (Scent leaf) was washed using tap water from the laboratory and then air dried at room temperature for 14 days. The dried leaves of *Ocimum gratissimum* were crushed into a fine powder using electric blender. 10g of the fine

powder was weighed and then mixed well in a 1 L beaker containing 40 mL of distilled water, covered with aluminium foil paper tightly and kept undisturbed in the laboratory for seven (7) days at room temperature. After maceration, it was filtered using Whatman No 1 Filter paper which was further purified using solid phase extraction kit (SPE kit). The extract obtained was kept in the refrigerator for further analysis.

Preparation of Methanol and Ethanol Extract of Ocimum gratissimum

The freshly collected leaves of *Ocimum gratissimum* (Scent leaf) was washed using tap water from the laboratory and then air dried at room temperature for 7 days. The dried leaves of *Ocimum gratissimum* was crushed into a fine powder using a mortar. About 10g of the fine powder was weighed and then mixed well in a 1 liter conical flask containing 40 mL of Ethanol and 40 mL Methanol, covered with aluminium foil paper and kept for 7 days. The extract was filtered using whatman No 1 filter paper and further purified using Solid Phase Extraction (SPE) kit. SPE kit was used in this present study to further purify the active compounds of *Ocimum gratissimum* by means of removing most of the impurities through the selective SPE column sorbent manufactured by Phenomenex. The SPE is designed in such a way that the sorbent matrix traps/retains polar compounds based on three factors; i. Hydrophilic interaction, ii. π - π bonding, and iii. Hydrogen bonding and dipole-dipole interaction (The filtrate was stored in the refrigerator properly prior to analysis).

Isolation and Identification of Bacteria Pathogens

The urine samples were screened for the presence of urine pathogens approximately, 0.1mL of each urine sample was inoculated on MacConkey, Chocolate and Cysteine Lactose Electron Deficient (CLED) agar using spread plate technique, allowed to stand for five (5) minutes and incubated for 24 hours at 37 °C. Colonies were subjected to Gram stain and biochemical test (Cheesbrough, 2006)

Characterization of Organic Compounds in Ocimum gratissimum using (GC-MS)

Gas chromatography (GC) analysis was done using gas chromatography (Perkin-Elmer 8500), column specification and temperature programme are described as follows; column SE (10%) on chromasorb W, column material S.S, column length 4 metres, internal diameter 1/8-inch, injector temperature 300°C, FID temperature 300°C, flow rate of N₂ 30ml/minute and temperature programming 100-250°C with 5°C/minute rise of temperature, final hold time 5 minutes.

Molecular Identification

Bacterial DNA Extraction

The bacterial DNA was extracted by a method as earlier described by Zakou u *et al.*, (2024) with minor modification. Ten (10) milliliters of an overnight broth culture of the bacterial isolate in 1mL Luria Bertani (LB) were spun at 14000rpm for 3 min. The supernatant was discarded, and the harvested cell pellet was resuspended in 1 mL sterile distilled water and transferred into 1.5 mL centrifuge tube and centrifuged at 14000rpm for 10 min. The supernatant was discarded carefully. The pellet was resuspended in 100 µL of sterile distilled water by vortexing. The tube was centrifuged again at 14000 g for 10 min, and the supernatant was discarded carefully. The cells were re-suspended in 500µL of normal saline and heated at 95°C for 20 min. The heated bacterial suspension was cooled on ice for 10mins and spun for 3 min at 14000rpm. The supernatant containing the DNA was transferred to a 1.5mL microcentrifuge tube and stored at -20°C for other downstream reactions.

DNA quantification

The extracted genomic DNA was quantified using the Nanodrop 1000 spectrophotometer. The software of the equipment was launched by double clicking on the Nanodrop icon. The equipment was initialized with 2µL of sterile distilled water and blanked using normal saline. 2µL of the extracted DNA was loaded onto the lower pedestal, the upper pedestal was brought down to contact the extracted DNA

on the lower pedestal. The DNA concentration was measured by clicking on the “measure” button (Abimiku *et al.*, 2019).

DNA Amplification by Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)

The single-plex polymerase chain reaction (PCR) was performed in 45 μL total volume using the ABI 9700 Applied Biosystems thermal cycler, containing 2.5 μL MgCl_2 (50 mM), 2.5 μL 10 \times buffer, 0.9 μL of each primer (2.7 μM), 8 mM of dNTPs, 0.5 μL Taq DNA polymerase (Zymo research, USA) and 5 μL of DNA template. Amplification was carried out in the following program: an initial denaturation step at 95°C for 5 minutes, followed by 40 denaturation cycles at 94°C for 1 min, annealing at 55°C for *bla*_{CTXM-II}, 58°C for *bla*_{CTX-M} and *bla*_{CTX-M-II}, 56°C for *bla*_{SHV}, and *bla*_{TEM} for 30s and extension at 68°C for 30s, and a final extension step at 68 °C for 10 minutes.

Detection of all the amplified genes by Agarose Gel Electrophoresis

Two percent (2%) agarose gel was used to resolve DNA fragment. This was prepared by combining 2g agarose in ten times concentration of tris-borate ethylene diamine tetraacetate (10mL 10XTB-EDTA) buffer and 90ml sterile distilled water in 250mL beaker flask and heating in a microwave for 2 minutes until the agarose is dissolved. Exactly 0.7 μL of ethidium bromide was added to the dissolved agarose solution with swirling to mix. The gel was then poured onto a mini horizontal gel electrophoresis tank and casting combs was inserted. The gel was allowed to set for 30 minutes. The casting combs were carefully removed after the agarose gel had solidified completely. One times concentration (1X) TBE buffer was added to the reservoir until it covered the agarose gel. Precisely 8 μL of gel tracking dye (bromophenol blue) was added to 10 μL of each sample with gentle mixing. The sample was loaded onto the wells of the gel at a concentration of 10 μL , the mini horizontal electrophoresis gel setup was covered and electrodes connected. Electrophoresis was carried out at 100-200mA for one hour. At the completion of electrophoresis, the gel was removed from the buffer and visualized under UV light and documented.

Table 1: Primer and oligonucleotide sequences of the used

Target genes	Sequence	Amplicon size	References
<i>blaTEM</i>	5'-TCGGGGAAATGTGCGCG-3' R ₃ '-TGCTTAATCAGTGAGGCACC-5'	972	Abrar <i>et al.</i> , 2019
<i>blaSHV</i>	5'-GGGTTATTCTTATTTGTCGC-3' R 3'-TTAGCGTTGCCAGTGCTC-5'	615	Abrar <i>et al.</i> , 2019
<i>blaCTX-M</i>	5'-ACGCTGTTGTTAGGAAGTG-3' R 3'-TTGAGGCTGGGTGAAGT-5'	757	Abrar <i>et al.</i> , 2019
<i>blaCTX-M-1</i>	5'-TTAGGAAGTGTCGCCGCTGTA-3' R 3'-CGGTTTTATCCCCACAAC-5'	197	Abrar <i>et al.</i> , 2019
<i>blaCTX-M-4</i>	5'-GACAAAGAGAGTGCAACGGATG-3' R 3'-TCAGTGCGATCCAGACGAA-5'	501	Abrar <i>et al.</i> , 2019

Susceptibility Test Using Agar Well Diffusion Method

Agar well diffusion method as describes by Ubafie and Ejale, (2018) was used to determine the effect of the plant extracts on the test organisms. It was applied in testing the multidrug resistant bacteria for their antimicrobial susceptibility based on diameter zone of inhibition on agar plates. In this method, Petri dish plates containing 20mL of Mueller Hinton agar was prepared. The overnight broth culture was diluted using normal sterile saline to a turbidity equivalent to 0.5 McFarland standards. And then 100µL of overnight culture suspension was placed on solidified Mueller Hinton agar plates using a sterile micropipette. A sterile glass spreader under aseptic condition was used to evenly distribute the test suspension on the Mueller Hinton agar. About 4mm wells were cut using a sterile cork borer and then 40µL of the treatment (plant extract) was added to the wells. The plates were properly labelled accordingly and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The antibacterial activity was assayed by measuring the diameter zone of inhibition formed around the well and interpreted in accordance with the susceptibility break point as earlier described by CLSI (2022).

Determination the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

Minimum inhibitory concentration of the plant extract was determined by broth micro-dilution method in peptone water using a 96

well microlitre plates. Thirty millilitre of sterile peptone water was transferred into a Petri dish. An 8-tip multichannel pipette was used to transfer 100µL of the sterile medium into a 96-well microlitre plates. Next, 100µL of the antimicrobial solution (extract) was transferred into the wells in column 1, and then mixed well making it a 1:2 dilution of the extract. 100µL was transferred from column 1 into column 2 using a multichannel pipette making it a 1:4 dilution of the extract. This was repeated up to column 9 making it 1:512 dilution of the extract. Column 10 served as growth control. A drop of a diluted culture was introduced into the different wells using a 200µL pipette leaving well 11 as sterility control. A lid was placed on the plate, and the plate wrapped with a cling film to prevent drying overnight and the plate incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Result was checked for the concentration that just inhibited the bacteria (MIC).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The result in table 2 shows the cultural and biochemical test on urine isolates of patients attending Federal University Teaching Hospital, Lafia Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The table indicates that *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella* and *Proteus* were isolated. The result in table 3 and 4 of the organic compounds in *O. gratissimum* shows that the organic compound with the most abundant in methanol extract is 3-Methyl-4-isopropylphenol (52.281%), and the least is Heptanoic acid, 3-methylbutyl ester, 4-Methyl-cyclohex-2-en-1-ol (1.789%). While the most abundant and least in ethanol extract is 3-Methyl-4-isopropylphenol Phenol, 2-methyl-5-(1-methylethyl) (59.615%) and 5-Hydroxy-2,2,6,6-tetramethyl-4-cyclohexene-1,3-dione (2.140%) respectively. Result of the diameter zone of inhibition of *Ocimum gratissimum* against *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in table 5 shows that *klebsiella pneumoniae* was susceptible to ethanol extract of *Ocimum gratissimum* with a diameter zone of inhibition of 12mm followed by aqueous extract and methanol with diameter zone of inhibition of 10.2mm and 9mm respectively at 250mg/mL, while the least activity was observed in 62.5mg/mL with diameter zone of inhibition of 2.7mm in water extract of *O. gratissimum*

For *Escherichia coli*, the highest activity was observed in methanol, aqueous, and ethanol at 250mg/mL. The diameter zone of inhibition is 13.5mm, 11.8mm, and 11mm respectively and the least activity was 3mm at 62.5mg/mL in methanol extract of *O.gratissimum* For *Proteus mirabilis*, the largest inhibition zones were observed in aqueous, methanol and ethanol extract of *O. gratissimum* at 250mg/mL, the diameter zone of inhibition is 11mm, 10.9mm, and 10.3mm respectively, while the least activity is 2.3 at 62.5mg/mL in methanol extract of *O. gratissimum*. The result of minimum inhibitory concentration as shown in table 6 revealed that the extract inhibited the growth of the urine isolates and the MIC values ranged between 62.5-31.3mg/mL.

Table 2: Identification of Isolates using Biochemical Tests & Cultural Characteristics

S/N	Gram Reaction	Catalase	Oxidase	Coagulase	Indole test	Citrate test	Cultural Characteristics	Suspected isolates
1.	-	+	-	-	+	-	Creamy mucoid on chocolate Agar, Lactose Fermenters on CLED & MacConkey agar	<i>E. coli</i>
2.	-	+	-	-	-	+	Creamy colonies on chocolate, lactose Fermenters on CLED & MacConkey agar	<i>Klebsiella</i>
3.	-	+	-	-	-	+	Creamy pigmented colonies on chocolate agar, non-Lactose Fermenters on MacConkey & CLED agar	<i>Proteus</i>

- = negative, + = positive,

Table 3: Organic compounds in methanol extract of *Ocimum gratissimum*

Peak	Compound names	RT (min)	PH	Quantity (%)
1	P-Cymene O-Cymene	10.041	1349695	4.187
2	Terpinene	11.455	3647049	9.734
3	Heptanoic acid, 3-methylbutyl ester,4-Methyl-cyclohex-2-en-1-ol Thymol	18.035	415589	1.789*
4	3-Methyl-4-isopropylphenol	21.225	4599604	52.281**
5	Bicyclo[5.2.0]nonane, 2-methylene- 4,8,8-trimethyl-4-vinyl-	24.072	1149174	3.766
6	Naphthalene, 1,2,3,5,6,7,8,8a-octahydro-1,8a-dimethyl-7-(1-methylethenyl)-	26.167	806287	2.934
7	1-Methoxy-3-(2-hydroxyethyl) nonane	36.019	1056695	1.944
8	n-Hexadecanoic acid	37.546	573505	2.190
9	Phytol	38.428	2855798	4.380
10	9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid	38.703	1067939	3.995
11	Thymol 3-Methyl-4-isopropylphenol	40.273	1396588	8.162
12	Squalene	43.363	1435851	4.637
	Supraene			

Table 4: Organic compounds in ethanol extract of *Ocimum gratissimum* (Scent leaves)

Peak #	Compound names	RT (min)	PH	Quantity (%)
1	O-Cymene p-Cymene	10.035	1149899	4.475
2	Terpinene	11.442	2256162	7.579
3	5-Hydroxy-2,2,6,6-tetramethyl-4-cyclohexene-1,3-dione Thymol	19.999	425990	2.140*
4	3-Methyl-4-isopropylphenol	21.207	4138037	59.615**
	Phenol, 2-methyl-5-(1-methylethyl)			
5	Caryophyllene	24.065	734616	3.050
6	Naphthalene, decahydro-4a-methyl-1-methylene-7-(1-methylethenyl)-	26.167	538773	2.381
7	n-Hexadecanoic acid	37.558	841003	2.502
8	Phytol	38.428	6398569	12.445
	Malonic acid, neopentyl tridecyl ester			
9	9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, ethyl ester	38.722	1469364	5.812

RT= Retention time, PH= Peak height, * = least quantity,
 ** = Most abundant quantity

Table 5: Diameter of zones of inhibitions of *Ocimum gratissimum* on urine isolates in mm (mg/mL)

Isolates	Solvent	250	125	62.5	31.3	p-value
<i>K. pneumonia</i>	Water	10.2±1.2	5.7±0.6	2.7±0.6	0.0±0.0	<0.003
	Ethanol	12.0±1.0	5.0±1.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	<0.007
	Methanol	9.0 ± 1.0	3.0±1.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	<0.009
<i>E. coli</i>	Water	11.8±0.3	10.7±0.6	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	<0.002
	Ethanol	11.0±0.5	5.0±1.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	<0.008
	Methanol	13.5±0.6	7.0±1.0	3.0±1.0	0.0±0.0	<0.005
<i>P. mirabilis</i>	Water	11.0±1.0	6.3±1.5	3.5±0.5	0.0±0.0	0.06
	Ethanol	10.3±0.5	5.3±1.5	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.09
	Methanol	10.9±0.8	5.0±1.7	2.3±0.6	0.0±0.0	<0.03

< P-0.05

Table 6: Minimum Inhibitory Concentrations of *O. gratissimum* on the Isolates

Isolates	Methanol mg/mL	Ethanol mg/mL	Water mg/mL
<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	62.5	31.3	62.5
<i>E. coli</i>	31.3	31.3	62.5
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	31.3	62.5	31.5

Plate 1: Agarose gel electrophoresis of the amplified bacterial isolates. Lane NC represents Negative; Lane KI expression of the *16SrRNA*(700bp) of *Klebsiella* species gene, Lane PI expression of the *16SrRNA*(523bp) *Proteus mirabilis* gene and Lanes EC1 EC2 and EC3 expression

of the *16SrRNA*(147bp) *Escherichia coli* gene. Lane M represents 1500bp DNA molecular ladder.

Plate 2: Agarose gel electrophoresis of the amplified gene. Lane K_I, P_I and EC₃ represent the expression of *blaTEM* gene. Lane M represents the 1500bp DNA molecular ladder.

blaCTX-M-4 (501bp)

Plate 3: Agarose gel electrophoresis of the amplified gene. Lane P_I and Lane EC₃ represent the expression of the *blaCTX-M-4* gene. Lane M represents 1500bp DNA molecular ladder.

Plate 4: Agarose gel electrophoresis of the amplified gene. Lane EC₁ and Lane EC₂ represent the expression of the *blaSHV* gene. Lane M represents 1500bp DNA molecular ladder.

Agarose gel electrophoresis of the amplified gene. Lane K₁, EC₁ and Lane EC₂ represent the expression of the *blaCTX-M-1* gene. Lane M represents 1500bp DNA molecular ladder.

DISCUSSION

Plants have been used since time immemorial for the therapeutic purposes particularly infectious diseases caused by pathogenic organisms. Urinary tract infection is a prevalent infectious disease known to affect people of all ages and is one of the prominent causes of morbidity. It affects both male and female but with a higher incidence among females. Young females involved in sexual activity are the most vulnerable, whereas the other groups are at risk, including older patients. Urinary tract infections are serious community health concerns which affects millions of people worldwide. Variation in the epidemiology of UTIs can be attributed to disparities in healthcare systems, diverse lifestyles, differences in geographical location, lack of public awareness, and insufficient access to clean water (Al-Hilu and Al-Shujairi, 2024).

Escherichia coli has been implicated as the most common cause of UTIs followed by other organisms such as *Klebsiella* spp *Proteus*, these pathogens have developed resistance to a wide range of commonly used antibiotics, ranging from augmentin, ciprofloxacin, amoxicillin, and gentamycin.

Recent report indicates a sharp increase in the rate of drug resistance to most of the commonly used antimicrobial agents especially in both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, due to the inappropriate use of antibiotics (Belete, 2020). The results obtained based on cultural and biochemical characteristics indicates that the isolated bacteria were gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Proteus mirabilis* as shown in (Table 2). This study is in agreement with the study conducted by Dharati (2021). In a hospital setting, the etiology and antimicrobial susceptibility pattern of uropathogens has evolved recently. Urinary tract infection has a huge burden on health care systems due to high prevalence of infection in both community and nosocomial settings (Sathiya, 2023). In methanol extract of *Ocimum gratissimum* as presented in Table 3, the most abundant were 3-methyl-4-isopropylphenol (52.281%), and Terpinene (9.735%), while the least abundant were Heptanoic acid, 3-methylbutyl ester, 4-methyl-cyclohex-2-en-1-ol (1.789%), and 1-methoxy-3-(2-hydroxyethyl)nonane (1.944%).

Result of the characterization of *Ocimum gratissimum* using Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) reveal that the most abundant compounds in ethanol extract of *Ocimum gratissimum* as presented in table 4 were 3-methyl-4-isopropylphenol (59.451%), Phytol (12.445%), and Terpinene (7.579%), while the least abundant were Naphthalene, decahydro-4a-methyl-1-methylene-7-(1-methylethenyl)-(2.381%), and n-Hexadecanoic acid (2.502%). All the compounds and their derivatives recovered from this present study possess antimicrobial and antiviral inhibitory potentials. Furthermore, this study revealed that ethanol was best for extraction of compound groups such as hydrophobic aromatics and conjugated fatty acids as evidenced in the results since these compounds constitute >60% abundance in the ethanol extract. In addition, this study also observed that while ethanol was able to recover more light-chained oil-derived compounds, the solvent methanol fared better for extracting more heavy chained polymeric hydrocarbons. Result of the susceptibility pattern of the extract against the isolates revealed that the extract exhibited considerable activity. The result of the diameter zone of

inhibition of *O. gratissimum* against *Klebsiella* and *proteus* as shown in Table 4 revealed that the isolates susceptible to the both water, ethanol, and methanol extracts in concentration of 250mg/mL. The present study shows that the activity was concentration dependent. There was a statistical difference between the isolates against the concentrations $p < 0.05$. Low activity from this study against the tested organisms from urinary tract could be caused by factors such as source of isolation, laboratory condition, and standard methodology (Otokunefor and Dappa, 2017). This study however showed a promising result with respect to the use of both water and ethanol extracts of *Ocimum gratissimum* in the treatment of multidrug resistant *Proteus mirabilis*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Klebsiella* urinary tract infection bacterial isolates.

This is in contrast to the study by Otokunefor and Dappa, (2017), who revealed that ethanol extract of *Ocimum gratissimum* showed better activity than aqueous extract of *Ocimum gratissimum*. At the lowest concentration of 31.3mg/mL no activity was observed with diameter zone of inhibition of 00mm. There was a statistical difference between the isolates against the concentrations at $p < 0.05$. The result of the diameter zone of inhibition of *O. gratissimum* against *Proteus mirabilis* as shown in Table 5. The isolate was resistant to water, ethanol and methanol extract at the highest concentration of 31.3mg/mL. There was no statistical difference between the isolates against the concentrations at $p < 0.05$. The present study revealed that water and ethanol was a better extraction solvent, and this is in agreement with the study by Lapornik *et al.* (2005). In their study, water was a good extraction solvent against urinary tract pathogens. The findings from the present study revealed that the susceptibility pattern of the extract on the different test organisms and the concentration of the extracts revealed that the diameter zone of inhibition decreases with decrease in concentration of the extracts and increase with increased in concentration of the extracts. This is in line with the study by Farnsworth, (1993). They reported that active compound could be present in insufficient quantities in extract which may not revealed any antimicrobial activity on pathogens.

The higher the concentration, the higher the antimicrobial activity and the lower the concentration, the lower the antimicrobial activity. Result of both the minimum inhibitory concentration revealed that the extract of *O. gratissimum* inhibited the urine pathogens at a higher concentration. It was also revealed that each of the isolates showed different level of antimicrobial activity that inhibited that growth. The MIC values ranged between 62.5-31.3 mg/mL (table 6). This conforms with the study by Uchejeso *et al.* (2022).

CONCLUSION

The present study revealed that *Escherichia coli*, *Proteus mirabilis*, and *Klebsiella* were implicated as the prevalent organisms from urinary tract of patients attending Federal University Teaching Hospital, Lafia. Continues testing and determination of antimicrobial activity especially from medicinal plants are important for the selection of appropriate antimicrobial agent for the treatment of infections caused by multidrug resistant bacteria. The study also revealed that *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella* and *proteus* were susceptible to both aqueous and ethanolic extracts of *Ocimum gratissimum* at high concentration, while the organisms were resistant to extract of *Ocimum gratissimum* at lower concentrations. The study also revealed that the plants contain important parameters that possess antibacterial property which could be used as an alternative for the management of UTIs.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. Additional studies involving larger sample sizes, diverse geographical locations, and more bacterial strains are recommended to validate and generalize the findings.
- ii. There is a need to standardize the extraction process (solvent type, concentration, and temperature) to optimize the yield and activity of active compounds.
- iii. Future studies should isolate and purify specific bioactive components of *Ocimum gratissimum* to identify the most effective antibacterial agents.

- iv. Assess the cytotoxicity and safety profile of *O. gratissimum* extracts through in vivo animal models or cell-line studies before recommending clinical application.
- v. Based on demonstrated activity, research into developing pharmaceutical formulations (e.g., capsules, creams, or syrups) from *Ocimum gratissimum* should be pursued.
- vi. The use of plant-based antimicrobials, especially for drug-resistant UTIs, should be considered for integration into primary health care systems in Nigeria and other developing countries.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to God Almighty for the knowledge and strength

Conflict of interests

There is no conflict of interest

Funding

This research work was funded by the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFUND).

Authors contribution

Peter contributed in the research design and the writing process. Safiya Sani conducted the laboratory work while Uyi reviewed the manuscript.

REFERENCES

- Abass, S.K., Ali, M.R., & Authman, S.H. (2014). Isolation of Multi Antibiotics Resistance *Escherichia coli* from urinary tract infection and the detection of *PapC* and *fimH* virulence genes by Polymerase chain reaction Technique. *Diyala Journal for Pure Sciences*, 10 (1), 1121-1127.
- Abdullahi, M. (2012). Phytochemical Constituents and Antimicrobial and Grain Protectant Activities of Clove Basil (*Ocimum gratissimum* L.) Grown in Nigeria, *International Journal of Plant Research*, 2(1), 51-58. doi: 10.5923/j.plant.20120201.08.

- Abimiku, R.H., Ngwai, Y.B., Nkene, I.H., Basse, B.E., Tsaku, P.A., Ibrahim, T., Tama, S.C., Ishaleku, D., & G. Pennap R.I. (2019). Molecular Diversity and Extended Spectrum Betalactamase Resistance of Diarrheagenic *Escherichia coli* from Patients Attending Selected Health Care Facilities in Nasarawa State, Nigeria; *International Journal of Pathogen Research*, 3(1): 1-18.
- Abrar, S., Noor, U.A., & Huma, L. (2019). Distribution of blaCTX – M, blaTEM, blaSHV and blaOXA genes in Extended-spectrum-β-lactamase-producing Clinical isolates: A three-year multi-center study from Lahore, Pakistan. *Antimicrobial Resistance and Infection Control*, 8(1) DOI: [10.1186/s13756-019-0536-0](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13756-019-0536-0)
- Al-Hilui, S. A, & Al-Shujairi, W, H. (2024). Effectiveness of Medicinal Plant Extract against Pathogenic Bacteria in the Prevention and Treatment of Urinary Tract Infections. *Journal of Pure and Applied Microbiology*, 18(1), 711-721.
- Belete, M.A. (2020). Bacterial Profile and ESBL Screening of Urinary Tract Infection Among Asymptomatic and Symptomatic Pregnant Women Attending Antenatal Care of Northeastern Ethiopia Region. *Infectious Drugs Resistant*. 13, 2579-2592. doi: 10.2147/IDR.S258379
- Cheesbrough, Monica. (2006). District laboratory practice in tropical countries (Part 2, 2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- CLSI. (2022): Epidemiology Cut off Values (ECVS). Their Stewardship.
- Dharati, S. (2021). Microbiological Profile and Antibigram of Uropathogens Isolated at a Tertiary Care Hospital. *JKIMSU*, 10(1), 15-26.

- Farnsworth, N.R. (1993). Biological approaches to the screening and evaluation of natural products. In: Rasoanaivo P, Ratsimamanga Urver S (Eds) *Biological evaluation of plants with reference to the Malagasy Flora*, 35-43, Madagascar
- Foxman, B. (2003). "Epidemiology of urinary tract infections: incidence, morbidity, and economic costs," *Disease-a-Month*. 49(2), 53-70.
- Justyna, B., Olga, S., & Prezemyslaw, B. (2012). Role of Uropathogenic *E. coli* virulence factors in development of Urinary Tract Infection and kidney damage. *International Journal of Nephrology*. doi: [10.1155/2012/681473](https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/681473)
- Kataria, M. & Singh, L. (1997). Hepatoprotective effect of Liver 52 and Kumaryasava on carbon tetrachloride induced hepatic damage in rats. *Indian Journal of Experimental Biology*, 35, 255-57.
- McMurry, L.M., & Levy, S.B. (2011). The periplasmic protein mppA is not involved in regulation of marA in *Escherichia coli*. *Antimicrobial Agent and Chemotherapy*, 55, 4939-4942.
- Mishra, M.P., Debata, N.K., & Padhy, R.N. (2013). Surveillance of multidrug resistant uropathogenic bacteria in hospitalized patients- an Indian study. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedical*, 3, 315-324.
- Monali, P. M., Sibanarayan R., Shasank, S. S., Goutam, G., Debajyoti, D., & Rabindra, N. P. (2015). In vitro antibacterial activity of crude extracts of 9 selected medicinal plants against UTI causing MDR bacteria. *Journal of King Saud University Science*, 29(20), 84-95.

- Nicolle, L.E. (2002). "Urinary tract infection in geriatric and institutionalized patients," *Current Opinion in Urology*, 12(1), 51–55.
- Nielsen, F. H. (1999) Ultratrace minerals. In *Modern nutrition in health and disease*, 9th ed. 283–303.
- Otokunefor, K., & Dappa, B. (2017). Antibacterial Evaluation of Nigerian *Ocimum Sanctum* Leaf Extracts against Bacterial Isolates Associated with Urinary Tract Infection. *Nigerian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Applied Science Research*, 6(1), 19–25.
- Sadler, A.I., Chiang, T., Kurihara, J.T., Rothblatt, J., & Silver, P. (1989). "A yeast gene important for protein assembly into the endoplasmic reticulum and the nucleus has homology to DnaJ, an *Escherichia coli* heat shock protein." *Journal of Cell Biology*, 109(61), 2665–2675.
- Sathiya, S.K. (2023). Bacteriological Profile and Antibiogram of Urinary Tract Infection in a Tertiary Care Hospital. *International Journal of Microbiology and Mycology*, 17(20), 1-5
- Stamm, W.E., & Norrby, S.R. (2001). Urinary Tract Infection: disease panorama and challenges. *Journal of Infectious Disease*, 183(1), 51-54
- Ubafie, M.O., & Ejale, A.U. (2018). Antimicrobial Activity and Quantitative Analysis of *Ocimum gratissimum* on Some Pathogenic Bacteria. *Issues in Biological and Pharmaceutical Research*. 6,17-22.
- Uchejeso, M.O., Favour, O.B., Poncheng, W., Susan, P.U., Eno, C.M., Susan, J.N., & Uju, U.A. (2022). Urinary Tract Pathogens: Analysis and Antimicrobial Effects of *Ocimum*

gratissimum Leaf. *Journal of Nutritional Food Science and Technology*, 3(2), 1-13

- Ulett, G.C., Totsika, M., Schaale, K., Carey, A.J., Sweet, M.J., & Schembri, M.A. (2013). Uropathogenic *Escherichia coli* virulence and innate immune responses during urinary tract infection. *Current Opinion in Microbiology*, 16, 100-107.
- Yatouli, M. (2010). Population structure of gut *Escherichia coli* and its role in development of extra-intestinal infections. *Iranian Journal of Microbiology*, 2(2), 59-72. PMID: [PMC3279776](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/3279776/)
- Zakou, A.T., Ngwai Y.B., Nkene I.H., Ishaleku D., Abimiku R.H., & Ekeleme I.K. (2024). Antimicrobial Resistance and Phenotypic Detection of Extended Spectrum Beta-Lactamase in *Escherichia Coli* from Children with Cases of Diarrhea in Nasarawa-South, Nasarawa State, Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology*, 16(8), 24-32.
<https://doi.org/10.9734/ajbgmb/2024/v1i6i8398>.